

Biological Perspectives of “Trade-Off” Between Ageing and Cancer

¹*Abhay Kumar Pandey, ²Abha Pandit, ³Deepti Pandey Bahuguna, ⁴B.L. Pandey

¹*Abhay Kumar Pandey, ²Abha Pandit, ³Deepti Pandey Bahuguna, ⁴B.L. Pandey

¹*Tutor, Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Bhopal, MP. India.

²Asst.Prof. Department of Medicine, Index Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Indore, MP. India.

³ENT Specialist Krishna Hospital and Research Centre, Haldwani, Uttarakhand. India.

⁴Prof. Department of Pharmacology, Institute Of Medical Sciences, BHU, Varanasi UP. India.

*Corresponding author: Abhay Kumar Pandey E-mail: abhay.physiology@gmail.com

Received: April 2, 2015, Accepted: May 9, 2015, Published: May 9, 2015.

ABSTRACT

Varied facets of health and disease are networked in molecular biologic and physiologic mechanisms which are explored and understood only partly. The later task is formidable challenge for interdisciplinary biomedical research, particularly in respect to cancer. The mystical/divine coding for individual life span may be scientifically decoded amid biological networks. Trade-offs between cancer and other infirmities provide for reorganizing holistic medical thought with better objectivity. Bits of cumulated, traditional, and reductionist knowledge needs holistic interpretation to meet such goal. How medical strategies may selectively negotiate the networks to fetch benefit without becoming counter-productive, is major question. Available information on biological basis of trade-offs between cancer and ageing is briefly discussed. That has crucial implications to concept and design of preventive and remedial interventions, particularly, drugs.

Keyword: Aging and cancer; cancer-trade-offs; cholesterol and cancer; age related NADH oxidase.

INTRODUCTION: The Trade-Off

Human organism undergoes influence of factors promoting both positive and negative correlations among diseases. Comorbidity patterns develop as per the duration and level of exposures to such factors during certain periods of individual's life. Understanding of ageing related decline in human health/well-being, and evaluation of interventions aiming at increasing healthy longevity necessitates study of such factors and their mechanisms of action. Ageing linked chronic diseases have crucial implications to strategies increased life span by reducing cancer risk. Cellular mechanisms of tumor suppression, e.g. senescence and programmed cell death (apoptosis), also enhance ageing as indicated in experiments (1). Higher cancer risk is implied in increased longevity of population. Treatment of one disease may increase susceptibility to other diseases. In such “trade off”, certain factors favoring cancer increase longevity and are protective against age-linked diseases, unless cancer actually occurs. Hence, eradication of cancer risk simply would prolong lifespan. Bearing of induced delay in some fundamental ageing process and prevention of chronic diseases and other disease risks, to longevity deserves better understanding. A trade-off indicates that longevity may be increased by changing balance with infirmities negatively correlated in regard to mortality risks.

Strategy for Epidemiologic Studies and Cholesterol /Cancer Relation

“Dependant competing risk paradigm” suits as approach for epidemiological investigation of connection among diseases. Rothenberg, adopting such approach revealed that reduction in cardiovascular disease related mortality, increases cancer related

mortality (2), which makes prediction of age specific increase of cancer risk difficult among older persons. Effect of changes in physiological and other variables affecting disease risks need due accounting (3). Merit of strategies to lower cholesterol in population remains debated (4). A, U shaped association among men indicates a higher total mortality rate for those with high as well as with low serum cholesterol (5). While hypercholesterolemia is established principal risk factor for coronary heart disease, lower cholesterol profile increases risk of cancer and non-coronary cardiac deaths (6-8). Possibilities exist that such association is secondary to confounding factors such as, serum retinol, vitamin E and beta carotene (9-12). The population includes people with genetically low concentrations as well as those with acutely or chronically depressed cholesterol as a result of inflammation, cancer or other diseases (7,13). How low cholesterol would increase cancer risk remains unsettled. Cholesterol may be promoter not initiator of carcinogenesis, as a risk factor and lower concentration limits that increase cancer are not settled. Serum cholesterol profiles correlated inversely with subsequent cancer related mortality in a Puerto Rican study (14). Relative weight, ventricular rate, haematocrit and cigarette smoking, made independent contributions in certain age groups. Such association was not seen in women (15). The gender based differences may be due to hormonal or metabolic mechanisms. An inverse association among centrally obese women and a positive association among peripherally obese women were found by Kritchevsky (16).

Several biological mechanisms have been proposed to explain inverse association between serum cholesterol and cancer mortality. A person's lipoprotein cholesterol profile is significantly associated with his predisposition to develop cancer, as shared genetic factor may presumably be involved (17). Low cholesterol levels may enhance carcinogenesis by affecting integrity of cellular membrane (18). Cruse et al (19), suggested that cholesterol may exert a conditional influence, acting indirectly via hormonal or immunologic mechanism. Also it may promote the action of an already initiated carcinogenic process. The biologic mechanism needs further research to reveal. Oxidized low density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL), affects many of the biologic events that occur during development of atherosclerotic lesions (20). Some oxLDL formed early, may influence gene expression. LDL that enters sub-endothelial space by transcytosis undergoes mild oxidative changes mediated by endothelial cells. It then stimulates expression of genes, e.g. endothelial adhesion molecules, chemotactic factors and colony stimulating factors, which result in attraction, retention, maturation and activation of monocytes, macrophages or T Lymphocytes. LDL oxidation is involved in mediating atherogenic risk of cigarette smoking, diabetes mellitus and atherogenic lipoprotein phenotype, characterized by the presence of small dense LDL (21). The adipose tissue is endocrine organ and plays important role in regulating energy metabolism and inflammation (22). Significance of lipid and its novel constituents e.g. Adiponectin, IgG and IgM types of autoantibodies to oxidized LDL (oxLDLIgG and oxLDLIgM), has been established in relation to cardiovascular disease (23,24). These may be considered biomarkers of lipid peroxidation (25). The oxLDL is toxic to endothelium and smooth muscle of arterial wall and is monocyte chemotactant (26). Markers of atherosclerotic vascular diseases show positive correlation with levels of oxLDLIgG (27). In contrast, protective role for oxLDLIgM in human cardiovascular diseases is proposed.

Cholesterol and Carcinogenesis:

Lipid peroxides damage DNA and can seriously impair repair capacity by direct interaction with repair proteins (28). Furthermore, they influence the intracellular redox equilibrium affecting several crucial signal transduction pathways (29). Adiponectin, serum immunoglobulinG, immunoglobulinM antibodies versus oxLDL levels (oxLDLIgG;oxLDLIgM), may play role in development and progression of various types of malignancies (23,30,31). Excess lipid peroxidation including oxLDL and anti-oxLDL auto-antibodies indicating oxidative stress, are believed to play key role in cancer development (27,32). Lower oxLDLIgG levels predicted decreased risk of acute myeloblastic leukaemia (AML), while higher oxLDLIgM predicted increased risk of AML. Low serum levels of oxLDL antibody can lead to uncontrolled cellular proliferation and reduction of apoptosis. Both such effects contribute to carcinogenesis. In contrast to their relation with cardiovascular and cerebro-vascular diseases, descending levels of oxLDL and oxLDL antibodies negatively correlate to different stages of esophageal cancer development. The elevation in oxLDLIgM had a positive potency (33). Another study by Eichholzer et al (34), revealed that increased mortality risk from cancer associated to low plasma cholesterol cannot be explained by confounding effect of antioxidant vitamins. The biological mechanism underlying the findings, the role of other risk factors of leukaemia e.g. smoking and exposure to certain chemicals are necessary to reveal. Whether oxLDLIgG as well as oxLDLIgM play causal role or

mere consequential role in AML may be ascertained for contemplating preventive and therapeutic interventions.

arNOX and Its Role

Age related NADH oxidase, (arNOX), are proteins that appear in cells and serum only after age of 30, rising thereafter to age of maturity in sixties and seventies (35). Five members of the TM-9 transmembrane protein family have origin from codes on different chromosomes. arNOX reduce molecular oxygen to superoxide anion and also to water. arNOX are shed from cell surface in to circulation generating superoxide and oxidizing serum lipoproteins (36,37). Reactive oxygen species are responsible for circulating oxidized LDL, and their clearance by macrophages through delivery to arterial wall (38). Eventually, atherosclerosis results advancing heart disease, arterial blockage, stroke and death.

The arNOX proteins, by generating superoxide and ROS, in direct contact with circulating lipoproteins as an electron source, are crucial contributor to cardiovascular disease. The arNOX provides a mechanism to transmit oxidative changes on cell surface to surrounding cells and circulating lipoproteins. Constitutive cell surface arNOX proteins, capable of oxidizing reduced quinones, can formulate a complete chain of electron transport from cytosol to oxygen at cell surface, with these proteins serving as terminal oxidases. These link accumulation of lesions in the mitochondrial DNA to cell surface accumulation of ROS, as one consequence of their stated role. By their location on cell surface (with capability to form superoxide in response to ageing), arNOX serve to propagate the ageing cascade to adjacent cells. The arNOX are inhibited by oxidized coenzyme Q (37). Coenzyme Q is obvious circulating molecule preventing ageing related oxidative changes in cell membrane and lipoproteins. Use of dietary coenzyme Q should be rational means to retard age related arterial lesions (36). The arNOX activity that increases susceptibility to atherosclerotic heart disease plays protective function against cancer, serving as key to the negative correlation between cancer and heart disease. The oxidized LDLs trigger apoptosis in collaboration with scavenger receptors and Toll like receptors (39-41). The state favors formation of foam cells, contributing to atherosclerosis. The heightened activity of arNOX results in increased apoptosis and autophagy, both processes being un-favourable to carcinogenesis.

Autophagy

Autophagy is inherent pathway in all such cells that contain lysosomal compartment, which carries out turnover of long lived proteins and cell organelles, also remodeling cytoplasm (42-44). Autophagy, is a cell response to stress, and can cause cell death under certain circumstances. Autophagic cell death is termed, type-II programmed cell death to distinguish it from apoptosis, and termed as type I programmed cell death (45). Autophagy is stimulated by stress, e.g. Starvation, change in cell volume, oxidative stress, accumulation of misfolded proteins, hormonal signals, irradiation, xenobiotics etc. In mammals, autophagy serves anti-ageing mechanism by eliminating organelle damaged by age associated peroxidation process (46). The protein breakdown in autophagy provides amino acids and other elements needed for intermediary metabolism and for biosynthetic pathways. Amino acids thus regulate the process. Autophagy and other lysosomal degradation processes decline during ageing, and keeping them active is relevant anti-ageing strategy (47).

Research on biology of ageing has focused on understanding molecular controls of autophagy. Several tumor suppressor

proteins (beclin 1, PTEN phosphatases, tensin homologue deleted from chromosome 10) appear to control autophagy. Tumor progression would thus be expected to decrease autophagy. A link between nutritional environment of cell and G-protein mediated control of autophagy exists. Amino acids control activation of Raf-1 kinase, leading to inhibition of G- α interacting protein (GAI), which regulates G-protein signaling involved in autophagy (48). The amino acids are physiological inhibitors of autophagy (49). A great variety of stimuli are also able to modulate autophagy. Most signaling pathways converge on common single target to control autophagy (50). Target receptor for Rapamycin TOR, is good candidate as “gate keeper” of autophagic pathway. It senses amino acids and ATP. It can also integrate hormonal signals via the class I-PI3 Kinase/Protein Kinase B pathway, which also regulate autophagy (51-53). Probably, a cyclic AMP-dependant- protein kinase (AMPK) that is sensitive to cytosolic AMP/ATP ratio, is involved in controlling autophagy (54). AMPK negatively modulates protein synthesis by impairing mTOR dependant signaling (55).

Control of autophagy by class I PI3 Kinase pathway in has implications for tumor progression, ageing and cell death. Dysregulation of of class I PI3K/PKB signaling is frequent in human cancers. Many elements in the later are onco-proteins or products of tumor suppressor genes (56-59). Reduced autophagy in cancer cells may be a mechanism to survive stress condition (50). Cancer cells would overcome limitation of nutrient supply by limiting autophagy (60). Autophagic machinery is triggered by intracellular aberrations, e.g. protein aggregates in cytosol and endoplasmic reticulum and the damaged mitochondria, for their recognition and removal. Roles of selective autophagy in cellular aging and death may better reveal upon understanding the molecular basis and help emergence of therapies for mitochondrial pathologies and other aberrations.

Waiting Research Perspectives

Aged organism bears modification of epigenome (61). The genes “inactivated” in effort to prevent aging prevail in cancers, e.g. progeroig genes WRN and laminA/C (62,63). The SirT2 deacetylase controls cell cycle progression and also supports chromosomal stability (64). SirT2 activity displays context dependancy in cancer, as per primary molecular target, stress and environmental millieu of cell (65,66). Adequate laboratory and clinical investigations may resolve the mystery.

Trade-off between cancer and ageing may reflect opposite manifestation of apoptotic and growth signaling pathways in cancer and ageing cells, balancing tumor suppression and tissue renewal. Tumor suppressor mechanisms e.g. p53 dependant induction of senescence and apoptosis, accelerate ageing (67,68). Mitochondrial theory, senescence theory and molecular inflammation theory are extensively investigated as contributory to the aging process (69,70). Interventions to impact lifespan and related diseases mandate comprehensive understanding of roles of molecular and cellular elements to in-vivo metabolism and homeostasis that may optimally be attained in the centenarians.

Linkage of oncogenes and tumor suppressors to epigenetic changes and/or altered metabolism in cancer cells need elaboration. Novel alternate metabolic pathways erupting in cancer cells indicate dynamic adaptations that intricately relate to tumorigenesis as well as progression (71). The role of hypoxia inducible key transcription factor and its target genes is seen to overlap mechanisms implicated in metabolic disarrays (72,73). Such interconnectivity may evolve cancer phenotypes, with

switching of massive pathways based on the oncogenic mechanisms that drive cancer. Sites of dismetabolism can be targeted by innovative therapies.

Cancer vulnerability may trade-off with ageing-unrelated infirmities, e.g. myocardial infarct, stroke etc., in which reduced apoptosis reduces mortality despite being promoter of cancer risk. The consequences of up-regulated programmes of cell death may be pro or anti-ageing, as per concurrent presence or absence of other ageing related pathologies (1). Normal or enhanced apoptosis and postponed-ageing phenotype, characterize longevity with reduced cancer risk (74,75). This is classically exemplified in “calorie restriction” anti-ageing treatment (76). What trade-offs contribute better to longevity, i.e. between cancer predisposition and one or other kind of infirmities and why, remain largely unexplored, but highly relevant perspectives of biomedicine.

Conflict of interest statement

There are no conflict of interests among the authors.

REFERENCES:

1. Campici J Cancer and aging: rival demons? *Nat Rev Cancer* 2003 3:339-349.
2. Rothenberg RB Competing mortality and progress against cancer *Epidemiology* 1994 5:197-203.
3. Yashin AI Manton K Stallard E Dependant competing risk: a stochastic process model *J Math Biol* 1986 24:119-140.
4. Smith GD Blood cholesterol and non-coronary mortality *Coron Artery Dis* 1993 4:860-866.
5. Jacobs D Blackburn H Higgins M et al Report of the conference on low blood cholesterol-mortality associations *Circulation* 1992 86:1046-1060.
6. Law MR Wald NJ Wu T Hackshaw A Bailey A Systematic under estimation of the association between serum cholesterol concentration and ischaemic heart disease in observational studies:Data from BUPA study *Br Med J* 1994 308: 363–366.
7. Mailahn EN Ferrell RE Naturally occurring low blood cholesterol and excess mortality *Coron Artery Dis* 1993 4:843-853.
8. Kritchevsky SB Kritchevsky D Serum cholesterol and cancer risk: an epidemiological perspective *Anu Rev Nutr* 1992 12:391-416.
9. Shekelle RB Tangney LC Rosso f AH Stamler J Serum cholesterol, beta carotene and risk of lung cancer *Epidemiology* 1992 3:282-287.
10. Kark JD Smith AH Hames CG Serum retinol and the inverse relationship between serum cholesterol and cancer *Br Med J* 1982 284:152-154.
11. Gerber M Segala C Astre C Scali J Serum cholesterol,plasma beta carotene and lung cancer *Epidemiology* 1994 5:380-381.
12. Willen WC Serum beta carotene: a mechanism or “yellow finger”? *Epidemiology* 1992 3:277-279.
13. Ettinger WH Harris T Cause of hypocholesterolaemia *Coron Heart Dis* 1993 4:854-859.
14. Garcia-Palmieri MR Sorlie PD Costas R jr Havlik RJ An apparent inverse relationship between serum cholesterol and cancer mortality in PuertoRico *Am J Epidemiol* 1981 114:29-40.

15. Schult AJ van Dijk CE Dekker JM Schouten EG Kok FJ Inverse association between serum total cholesterol and cancer mortality in Dutch civil servants *Am J Epidemiol* 1993 137:966-976.
16. Kritchevsky SB Dietary lipids and the low blood cholesterol-cancer association *Am J Epidemiol* 1992 135:509-520.
17. McMichael AJ Serum cholesterol and human cancer In, *Cancer and Nutrition*, Alfin-Slater RB, Kritchevsky D eds. 1991 New York Plenum Press p 141-158.
18. Oliver MF Serum cholesterol: the knave of hearts and the joker *Lancet* 1981 ii: 1090-1095.
19. Cruse P Lewin M Clark CG Dietary cholesterol is co-carcinogenic for human colon cancer *Lancet* 1979 i:752-755.
20. Chait A Low density lipoprotein oxidation and the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis *WJM* 1994 160 183-184.
21. Chait A Brazig RL Tribble DL Krauss RM Susceptibility of small dense LDL to oxidize modification in subjects with the atherogenic lipoprotein phenotype pattern B *Am J Med* 1993 94:350-356.
22. Li H Diao YT Li HQ Ma Q Cui J Zhou YS Li D The association between serum levels of oxLDL-IgG and oxLDL-IgM autoantibody with adult acute myeloblastic leukaemia *Lipids Health Dis* 2010 9:11-15.
23. Virella G Carter RE Saad A Crosswell EG Game BA DCCT/EDIC study group –Distribution of IgM and IgG antibodies to oxidized LDL in immune complexes isolated from patients with type-1 diabetes and its relationship with nephropathy *Clin Immunol* 2008 127:394-400.
24. Bar D Williams CJ Neuwirth AK Mantzoros CS Adiponectin in relation to malignancies: a review of existing basic research and clinical evidence *Am J Clin Nutr* 2007 86(suppl): 858s-866s.
25. Nishi K Itabe H Uno M Kitazuto KT Horiguchi H Shinno K Nagahiro S Oxidised LDL in carotid plaques and plasma associates with plaque instability *Atheroscler Thromb Vasc Biol* 2002 22:1649-1654.
26. Karvonen J Parivansalo M Kesaniemi YA Horkko S Immunoglobulin-M type of autoantibodies to oxidized LDL has an inverse relation to carotid artery atherosclerosis *Circulation* 2003 108:2107-2112.
27. Guyton KZ Kensler TW Oxidative mechanisms in carcinogenesis *Br Med Bull* 1993 49:481-483.
28. Brown NS Bicknell R Hypoxia and oxidative stress in breast cancer. Oxidative stress, its effects on the growth, metastatic potential and response to therapy of breast cancer *Breast Cancer Res* 2001 3 323-327.
29. Motta M Pistone G Franzone AM Romeo MA DiMauro S Giugno I et al Antibodies against oxLDL serum levels in patients with hepatocellular carcinoma *Panminerva Med* 2003 45:69-73.
30. Petridou E Mantzoros CS Dessypris N Dikaloti SK Trichopoulos D Adiponectin in relation to childhood myeloblastic leukaemia *British J Cancer* 2006 94:156-160.
31. Wang Y Li H Diao Y Li H Zhang Y Yin C et al Relationship between oxidized LDL antibodies and different stages of esophageal carcinoma *Arch Med res* 2008 39:760-767.
32. Uchida K 4-hydroxy-2-nonenal: a product and mediator of oxidative stress *Prog Lipid Res* 2003 42:318-343.
33. Diao Y Li H Li H Zhou Y Ma Q Wang Y Li D Association of serum levels of lipid and its novel constituents with the different stages of esophageal carcinoma *Lipids Health Dis* 2009 8:48 doi 10.1186/1476-511x-8-48.
34. Eichholzer M Stahelin HB Gutzwiller F Ludin E Bernasconi F Association of low plasma cholesterol with mortality of cancer at various sites in men: 17-y follow up of the prospective Basel study *Am J Clin Nutr* 2000 71: 569-574.
35. Morre DM Guo F Morre DJ An aging related cell surface NADH oxidase (arNOX) generates superoxide and is inhibited by coenzyme-Q *Mol Cell Biochem* 2003 254:101-109.
36. Morre DJ Morre DM Aging related cell surface ECTO-NOX protein arNOX, a preventive target to reduce atherogenic risk in the elderly *Rejuven Res* 2006 9:231-236.
37. Morre DJ Morre DM ECTO-NOX Proteins 2012. New York Springer.
38. Steinberg D Parthasarathy S Carew TE Khoo JC Witztum JL Beyond cholesterol: modifications of LDL that increase its atherogenicity *New Engl J Med* 1989 320:915-924.
39. Perham P *The Immune System* 2005, 2nd Ed, New York, Garland Science Publishing.
40. Hoffman R Benz EJ Silberstein L Heslop H Weitz J Anastasi J *Haematology: Basic Principles and Practice*. 2013, 6th ed. Ch. 146.
41. Lieberman M Marks AD *Basic Medical Biochemistry: A clinical approach*. 2009, 3rd ed. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. Philadelphia.
42. Dunn WA Jr Autophagy and related mechanisms of lysosome mediated protein degradation *Trends cell boil*, 1994 4:139-143.
43. Klionsky DT Ohsumi Y Vacuolar import of proteins and organelles from the cytoplasm *Anu Rev Cell Dev Biol* 1999 15:1-32.
44. Seglen PO Bohley p Autophagy and other vacuolar protein degradation mechanisms *Experientia* 1992 48:158-172.
45. Clarke PGH Development Cell Death : morphological diversity and multiple mechanisms *Anat embryo* 1990 181:195-213.
46. Bergamini E Cavallini G Donati A Gori Z The anti-aging effects of caloric restriction may involve stimulation of macroautophagy and lysosomal degradation and can be intensified pharmacologically *Biomed Pharmacother* 2003 57:203-208.
47. Cuervo AM Dice JF When lysosomes get old. *Exp Gerontol* 2000 35:119-131.
48. Ogier-Dennis E Petiot A Bauvy C Codogno P Control of the expression and activity of the G(alpha)- interacting protein (GAIP) in human intestinal cells *J biol chem* 1997 272 :24599-24603.
49. Van Sluijters DA Dubbelhuis PF Blommaart EFC Meijer AJ Amino acid dependant signal transduction *Biochem J* 2000 351: 545-550.

50. Ogier-Dennis E Codogno P Autophagy:a barrier or an adaptive response to cancer? *Biochim Biophys Acta* 2003 1603:113-128.
51. Dennis PB Jaeschke A Saitoh M Fowler B Kozma SC Thomas G mammalianTOR: a homeostatic ATP sensor *Science* 2001 294:1102-1105.
52. Marygold SJ Leever SJ Growth signaling:TSC takes its place *Current Biology* 2002 12: R785-R787.
53. Rohde J Heitman J Cardenas ME The TOR kinase link nutrient sensing to cell growth *J biol chem* 2001 276:9583-9586.
54. Hardie DG Carling D Carlson M The AMP activated/ SNF1 protein kinase subfamily:Metabolic sensors of eukaryotic cell ? *Anu Rev Biochem* 1998 67:821-855.
55. Bolster DR Crozier SJ Kimball SR Jefferson LS AMP-activated protein kinase suppresses protein synthesis in rat skeletal muscle through down regulated mammalian target of rapamycin(mTOR) signaling. *J boil chem.* 2002 277:23977-23980.
56. Lawlor MA Alessi DR PKB/Akt:a key mediator of cell proliferation *J Cell Sci* 2001 114: 2003-2010.
57. Testa J Bellacosa A AKT plays a central role in tumorigenesis *PNAS* 2001 98:10983-10985.
58. Vogt PK PI-3 Kinase, mTOR, protein synthesis and cancer *Trends Mol Med* 2001 7:482-484.
59. Weaver SA Ward SG Phosphoinositide 3 Kinase in the gut: a link between inflammation and cancer? *Trends Mol Med* 2001 7:455-462.
60. Izuishi K Kato K Ogura T Kinoshita T Esumi H Remarkable tolerance of tumor cells to nutrient deprivation:possible new biochemical target for cancer therapy *Cancer Res* 2000 60:6201-6207.
61. Ershler WB, Longo DL Aging and cancer: issues of basic and clinical science. *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 1997; 89(20):1489-97.
62. Agrelo R, Setien F, Espada J, Artiga MJ, Rodriguez M, Pérez-Rosado A, et al. Inactivation of the lamin A/C gene by CpG island promoter hypermethylation in hematologic malignancies, and its association with poor survival in nodal diffuse large B-cell lymphoma. *J Clin Oncol.* 2005 23:3940-7.
63. Agrelo R1, Cheng WH, Setien F, Ropero S, Espada J, Fraga MF et al. Epigenetic inactivation of the premature aging Werner syndrome gene in human cancer. *PNAS* 2006 103:8822-7.
64. Inoue T, Hiratsuka M, Osaki M, Yamada H, Kishimoto I, Yamaguchi S et al . SIRT2, a tubulin deacetylase, acts to block the entry to chromosome condensation in response to mitotic stress. *Oncogene.* 2007 26: 945-57.
65. Vaquero A1, Scher MB, Lee DH, Sutton A, Cheng HL, Alt FW et al SirT2 is a histone deacetylase with preference for histone H4 Lys 16 during mitosis. *Genes Dev.* 2006, 20:1256-61.
66. Fraga MF1, Ballestar E, Villar-Garea A, Boix-Chornet M, Espada J, Schotta G et al Loss of acetylation at Lys16 and trimethylation at Lys20 of histone H4 is a common hallmark of human cancer. *Nat Genet.* 2005 37:391-400.
67. Ukraintseva SV Yashin AI Individual aging and cancer risk: how are they related ? *Demogr res* 2003 9:163-196.
68. Ukraintseva SV Yashin AI Opposite phenotypes of cancer and aging arise from alternative regulation of common signaling pathways *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 2003a 1010:489-492.
69. Chen JH1, Hales CN, Ozanne SE . DNA damage, cellular senescence and organismal ageing: causal or correlative? *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2007;35:7417-28.
70. Pandey AK, Pandey G, Pandey SS and Pandey BL. Human Biology of Diet and Lifestyle Linked Chronic Inflammatory Non-Communicable Disease Epidemic – A Review. *Human Biology Review.* 2014; 3:25-42.
71. Van-Dong C Pollak M Why cancer and metabolism? Why now? *Cancer metabolism* 2013 1:1.
72. Pandey G, Pandey AK. Nutrition research perspectives in immune-mediated inflammatory disorders *Indian journal of rheumatology.* 2013; 8:30-36.
73. Masson N Ratcliffe PJ Hypoxia signaling pathways in cancer metabolism:the importance of co-selecting interconnected physiological pathways *Cancer Metabolism* 2014 2:3 doi.10.1186/2049-3002-2-3.
74. Campici J Aging and cancer cell biology *Aging Cell* 2008 7:281-284.
75. Yashin AI Ukraintseva SV Akushevich IV Arbeev KG Kulminski A Akushevich L Trade-off between cancer and aging:what role do other diseases play?Evidance from experimental and human population studies *Mech Aging Dev* 2009 130:98-104.
76. James SJ Muskhelishvili L Gaylor DW Turturro A Hart R Upregulation of apoptosis with dietary restriction:implications for carcinogenesis and aging *Environ Health Perspect* 1998 106:307-312.

Citation: Abhay Kumar Pandey et al. (2015). Biological Perspectives of “Trade-Off” Between Ageing and Cancer. *J. of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences.* V3I1. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.V3I1.03

Copyright: © 2015 Abhay Kumar Pandey. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.